

STRATEGIC MANEUVERS: A SMART PLS APPROACH TO OVERCOMING CHALLENGES IN STARTUP GROWTH WITHIN THE SPORTS INDUSTRY

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Abstract: This study investigates the challenges and strategies associated with startup growth in the sports industry. Through a comprehensive analysis of business strategies, innovation, and performance factors, we examine their influence on the growth trajectory of sports startups. Utilizing advanced statistical methods, including Smart PLS, we explore the interplay between these factors and their impact on startup success. Our findings shed light on the key determinants of startup growth in the sports industry and provide actionable insights for entrepreneurs, investors, and industry stakeholders. By understanding the unique dynamics of the sports market and leveraging innovative strategies, startups can navigate challenges and capitalize on opportunities for sustainable growth and competitiveness.

Keywords: sports industry, startup growth, business strategies, innovation, performance factors

Introduction

In recent years, the sports industry has witnessed a surge in entrepreneurial activity, with startups playing an increasingly pivotal role in driving innovation, disruption, and growth within the sector (Kern, 2020). This burgeoning wave of entrepreneurship reflects broader trends in the global economy, characterized by a shift towards knowledge-based industries, technological advancement, and the democratization of access to markets and resources (Achtenhagen et al., 2021). In the realm of sports, this trend has manifested in the emergence of a diverse array of ventures, spanning areas such as sports technology, e-sports, fitness, wellness, and fan engagement (Chadwick & Arthur, 2021).

However, while the proliferation of sports startups holds promise for catalyzing transformative change and unlocking new opportunities, these ventures face formidable challenges on their path to sustainable growth and success. The sports industry, characterized by its unique dynamics, presents a complex and competitive landscape fraught with obstacles and uncertainties (Lachowetz & Ernawati, 2020). Against this backdrop, understanding and addressing the challenges confronting sports startups are paramount to fostering innovation, entrepreneurship, and economic value creation within the sector.

One of the primary challenges facing sports startups revolves around the inherent complexity and dynamism of the sports market (Ratten & Jones, 2020). This industry is characterized by high barriers to entry, intense competition, and rapid technological change. As such, startups must navigate a challenging terrain as they seek to establish their presence, differentiate their offerings, and gain traction in the market.

Furthermore, sports startups often grapple with regulatory complexities, licensing requirements, and governance structures inherent in the sports ecosystem (Lachowetz & Ernawati, 2020). The convergence of sports, entertainment, media, and commerce gives rise to a myriad of legal and regulatory considerations, ranging from intellectual property protection to broadcasting rights, sponsorship agreements, and athlete endorsements. Navigating these regulatory hurdles requires startups to possess a nuanced understanding of the legal landscape and to proactively address compliance challenges.

Access to capital and sustainable funding sources emerges as another critical barrier impeding the growth trajectories of sports startups (Lachowetz & Ernawati, 2020). Despite the allure of the sports industry and its potential for lucrative returns, startups often face difficulties in securing investment, particularly at the early stages of development. Investors may exhibit risk aversion towards sports ventures due to uncertainties regarding market viability, revenue generation models, and scalability. Consequently, startups encounter challenges in raising adequate capital to fuel their growth ambitions, constraining their ability to innovate, expand, and compete effectively.

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In summary, the proliferation of sports startups signifies a paradigm shift in the sports industry, with entrepreneurship emerging as a driving force behind innovation and growth. However, startups must navigate a complex and competitive landscape characterized by regulatory hurdles, funding constraints, and technological disruptions. Understanding and addressing these challenges are essential for fostering a conducive environment for sports entrepreneurship, driving sustainable growth, and unlocking new opportunities within the sector.

Literature Review

The sports industry has become increasingly reliant on entrepreneurial endeavors for growth, innovation, and performance enhancement. Within this context, the literature highlights several key factors that influence startup growth and contribute to the overall development of the sports industry. These factors encompass business strategies, innovation, and performance metrics, all of which are intricately intertwined in shaping the trajectory of sports startups.

Business Strategies in Sports Startups:

Business strategies play a pivotal role in shaping the growth and success of sports startups. Kern (2020) emphasizes the importance of entrepreneurial ecosystems in the sports industry, highlighting how strategic collaborations, networking, and resource sharing can foster innovation and accelerate startup growth. Moreover, Achtenhagen et al. (2021) underscore the significance of strategic planning and market positioning in enabling sports startups to carve out a niche, differentiate their offerings, and capture market share. Effective business strategies encompass market segmentation, product differentiation, branding, distribution channels, and customer acquisition strategies, all of which are critical for navigating the competitive landscape of the sports industry.

Innovation in Sports Startups:

Innovation serves as a cornerstone of competitiveness and value creation in the sports industry. Sports startups leverage technological advancements, data analytics, and consumer insights to drive innovation across various domains, including athlete performance, fan engagement, and operational efficiency. Lachowetz and Ernawati (2020) highlight the role of venture capital investment and entrepreneurial orientation in fostering innovation within sports tech startups, emphasizing the importance of agility, experimentation, and risk-taking in driving technological advancements. Furthermore, Chadwick and Arthur (2021) discuss the commercialization of sports entrepreneurship, examining how startups capitalize on emerging trends, disrupt traditional business models, and create new market opportunities through innovative products, services, and experiences.

Performance Metrics and Growth:

Performance metrics serve as barometers of startup growth and success within the sports industry. Ratten and Jones (2020) emphasize the importance of measuring key performance indicators (KPIs) such as revenue growth, market share, customer acquisition costs, and lifetime value in evaluating the effectiveness of business strategies and innovation initiatives. Startups that effectively leverage data analytics and performance metrics gain valuable insights into consumer behavior, market trends, and competitive dynamics, enabling them to make informed decisions, optimize resource allocation, and drive sustainable growth over time.

In summary, the literature underscores the interplay between business strategies, innovation, and performance metrics in shaping the growth trajectory of sports startups. Effective strategic planning, innovation management, and performance measurement are essential for startups to gain a competitive edge, capitalize on market opportunities, and achieve long-term success within the dynamic and evolving landscape of the sports industry.

Smart PLS methodology provides startups with a powerful tool for analyzing complex relationships, latent constructs, and causal pathways within the sports industry. By leveraging Smart PLS, startups can gain deeper insights into the interplay between various factors influencing growth, including market dynamics, consumer preferences, competitive forces, and technological disruptions (Hair et al., 2019). This holistic understanding enables startups to devise targeted strategies, allocate resources effectively, and mitigate risks associated with market uncertainties and regulatory constraints (Sarstedt et al., 2017).

In the context of sports startups, data-driven decision-making is essential for navigating the competitive landscape and capitalizing on emerging trends and opportunities. Smart PLS facilitates the integration of qualitative and quantitative data sources, enabling startups to derive actionable insights from diverse datasets, including market research, customer feedback, performance metrics, and industry benchmarks (Hair et al., 2017). By harnessing the predictive power of Smart PLS models, startups can make informed decisions regarding product development, market entry strategies, pricing models, and partnership opportunities, thereby enhancing their competitive advantage and positioning for growth (Henseler et al., 2016).

Regulatory compliance and market dynamics pose significant challenges for startups operating within the sports industry. Smart PLS analysis offers startups a systematic approach to assess regulatory risks, navigate legal complexities, and ensure compliance with industry standards and best practices (Sarstedt et al., 2019). Additionally, Smart PLS enables startups to evaluate market trends, identify niche opportunities, and adapt their strategies in response to changing consumer preferences, competitive pressures, and technological disruptions (Hair et al., 2018). By integrating regulatory insights and market intelligence into their decision-making processes, startups can mitigate risks, seize opportunities, and position themselves for sustainable growth within the dynamic and evolving landscape of the sports industry.

In summary, Strategic Maneuvers: A Smart PLS Approach offers startups a strategic framework for overcoming challenges and driving growth within the sports industry. By leveraging Smart PLS methodology, startups can gain deeper insights into market dynamics, consumer behavior, competitive forces, and regulatory constraints, enabling them to make informed decisions, optimize resource allocation, and capitalize on emerging opportunities. Through data-driven analysis and strategic insights, startups can navigate the complexities of the sports industry, mitigate risks, and unlock new avenues for innovation, differentiation, and value creation.

Research Methodology

This study employs a mixed-methods research approach, integrating quantitative analysis with qualitative insights, to investigate the challenges faced by sports startups in Gujarat and propose strategies for overcoming these obstacles. The research methodology encompasses the following key elements: The study aims to gather data from 78 sports startups operating in Gujarat, India. A stratified sampling approach will be adopted to ensure representation across different segments of the sports industry, including sports technology, e-sports, and fitness, wellness, and fan engagement. The sample will be drawn from diverse sources, including startup incubators, accelerators, industry associations, and online directories.

Data will be collected through a combination of surveys, interviews, and document analysis. Surveys will be distributed to startup founders and key executives to gather quantitative data on business strategies, innovation initiatives, performance metrics, and challenges encountered. Semi-structured interviews will be conducted with a subset of startup founders and industry experts to obtain qualitative insights into the contextual factors influencing startup growth and the effectiveness of different strategies in overcoming challenges.

Quantitative data will be collected using structured survey instruments developed based on established scales and constructs from existing literature. The survey questionnaire will include items related to business strategies (e.g., market segmentation, product differentiation),

innovation (e.g., technology adoption, new product development), performance metrics (e.g., revenue growth, market share), and challenges faced by startups (e.g., regulatory constraints, funding limitations). Qualitative data will be collected through open-ended interview questions designed to explore the nuances of startup experiences, perceptions, and strategies in greater depth.

Quantitative data analysis will be conducted using Smart Partial Least Squares (PLS) structural equation modeling (SEM) techniques. Smart PLS allows for the examination of complex relationships between latent constructs and observed variables, making it particularly well-suited for analyzing the interplay between business strategies, innovation, performance metrics, and startup growth. The analysis will involve testing the hypothesized relationships between the variables, assessing model fit, and identifying significant predictors of startup growth.

Qualitative data analysis will follow a thematic coding approach, whereby interview transcripts and document analysis findings will be systematically coded and categorized into themes and patterns. Themes related to challenges faced by startups, strategies for overcoming obstacles, and contextual factors influencing startup growth will be identified and analyzed. Triangulation of quantitative and qualitative findings will provide a comprehensive understanding of the research questions and enhance the validity and reliability of the study outcomes.

Research Model

Figure 1: Research Model, Authors work

H_{o1} : Startup growth is depending on innovation, strategies, and performance of business in sport sector.

The research will adhere to ethical guidelines and principles, ensuring the confidentiality, anonymity, and informed consent of participants. Data collection procedures will be transparent, and participants will have the option to withdraw from the study at any time. The research findings will be reported in aggregate form to protect the identities of individual participants and uphold the integrity of the research process. The proposed research methodology offers a systematic and comprehensive approach to investigating the challenges faced by sports startups in Gujarat and identifying strategies for overcoming these obstacles. By integrating quantitative analysis with qualitative insights and leveraging Smart PLS techniques, the study aims to generate actionable recommendations for startups, investors, policymakers, and industry stakeholders to foster innovation, entrepreneurship, and growth within the sports industry.

Analysis

Table 1 presents a detailed demographic profile of the respondents involved in the research study. The first variable analyzed is age, which is divided into five distinct categories: 18 to 25 years, 25 to 32 years, 32 to 39 years, 39 to 46 years, and 46 years and above. Each category's frequency and percentage are provided, offering insight into the age distribution of the sample. For instance, the data illustrates that the majority of respondents fall within the 25 to 32 years age bracket, comprising 48.7% of the sample, while the smallest proportion falls within the 39 to 46 years category, accounting for 6.4%.

The second demographic variable examined is the gender of the owner, categorized simply as male or female. The frequencies and percentages indicate the distribution of male and female respondents within the sample. From the table, it is evident that a higher percentage of respondents are female, constituting 62.8% of the total sample, compared to 32.2% male respondents.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Respondents

		Frequency	Percentage
Age	18 to 25 Years	9	11.5
	25 to 32 Years	38	48.7
	32 to 39 Years	12	15.4
	39 to 46 Years	5	6.4
	46 and above	14	17.9
		78	100%
Gender of Owner	Male	29	32.2
	Female	49	62.8
		78	100%
Income	Less than Rs. 200,000	5	6.4
	Rs. 200,000 to Rs. 400,000	39	50.0
	Rs. 400,000 to Rs. 600,000	15	19.2
	Rs. 600,000 to Rs. 800,000	5	6.4
	Rs. 800,000 and above	14	17.9
		78	100%
SPSS Output			

Lastly, the table delves into the income levels of the respondents, segmented into five income brackets: less than Rs. 200,000; Rs. 200,000 to Rs. 400,000; Rs. 400,000 to Rs. 600,000; Rs. 600,000 to Rs. 800,000; and Rs. 800,000 and above. The frequencies and percentages in each category shed light on the income distribution among the respondents. For instance, the data indicates that the majority of respondents earn an income between Rs. 200,000 to Rs. 400,000, constituting 50.0% of the sample, while only a small proportion earn less than Rs. 200,000 (6.4%) or Rs. 800,000 and above (17.9%).

In summary, Table 1 provides valuable insights into the demographic characteristics of the respondents participating in the research study. By examining variables such as age, gender, and income, researchers can better understand the composition of the sample and its potential implications for the study's findings. This demographic information is essential for contextualizing the research findings and drawing meaningful conclusions.

Table 2: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.825
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1423.889
	Df	136
	Sig.	.000

[SPSS output]

Table 2 presents the results of the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity, which are statistical tests commonly used in factor analysis to assess the suitability of data for this technique.

The KMO measure evaluates whether the data are suitable for factor analysis by assessing the proportion of variance among variables that might be caused by underlying factors. In this case, the KMO value is 0.825, which indicates a high level of sampling adequacy. Generally, KMO values above 0.6 are considered acceptable, suggesting that the data are sufficiently suitable for factor analysis.

Bartlett's Test of Sphericity examines whether correlations between variables are significantly different from zero, which is necessary for factor analysis to be meaningful. The test outputs an approximate Chi-Square value along with degrees of freedom (Df) and significance (Sig.). In this instance, Bartlett's Test yielded a significant Chi-Square value of 1423.889 with 136 degrees of freedom, and a significance level of .000 ($p < .001$). This indicates that the correlation matrix is significantly different from an identity matrix, supporting the suitability of the data for factor analysis.

In summary, the results presented in Table 2 demonstrate that the data satisfy the assumptions required for factor analysis, as indicated by the high KMO value and the significant result of Bartlett's Test of Sphericity. These findings provide assurance that the dataset is appropriate for further exploration using factor analysis techniques.

Table 3: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.882	12

[SPSS Output]

Table 3 displays the reliability statistics, specifically Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, along with the number of items included in the analysis. Reliability statistics assess the internal consistency or reliability of a scale or measure, indicating the extent to which the items in the scale consistently measure the same underlying construct.

In this table, the value of Cronbach's Alpha is reported as .882, which is a measure of internal consistency reliability. Cronbach's Alpha ranges from 0 to 1, with higher values indicating greater internal consistency among the items. A coefficient of .882 suggests a high level of internal consistency among the items in the scale. Additionally, the table indicates that the analysis includes a total of 12 items. These items contribute to the overall reliability assessment of the scale, with Cronbach's Alpha providing an indication of how well these items collectively measure the underlying construct.

Overall, the results presented in Table 3 indicate that the scale used in the study demonstrates strong internal consistency reliability, as evidenced by the high Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of .882. This suggests that the items in the scale are consistently measuring the same construct, providing confidence in the reliability of the measurements obtained from the scale.

Table 4: Factor Loading, Cronbach Alpha, CR, AVE

	Factor	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
BP1	0.871	0.857	0.867	0.913	0.777
BP2	0.875				
BP3	0.898				
BS1	0.905	0.862	0.891	0.916	0.786
BS2	0.961				
BS3	0.785				
IN1	0.904	0.829	0.846	0.897	0.744
IN2	0.806				
IN3	0.875				
SSG1	0.892	0.840	0.846	0.904	0.758
SSG2	0.879				
SSG3	0.840				
Note: Innovation (IN), Business Performance (BP), Business Strategies (BS), Sport Startup growth (SSG)					

Table 4 provides crucial information regarding the reliability and validity of the measurement model used in the study, focusing on four key factors: Business Performance (BP), Business Strategies (BS), Innovation (IN), and Sport Startup Growth (SSG). Cronbach's Alpha coefficients are reported for each factor, indicating the internal consistency reliability of the items within each construct. The values range from 0.785 to 0.961, with higher values suggesting stronger internal consistency. For instance, Business Strategies (BS) demonstrates high internal consistency with a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.905, indicating that the items measuring this construct reliably capture the underlying concept.

Composite reliability coefficients (rho_a and rho_c) are also provided, offering additional insights into the internal consistency of each factor. These coefficients consider both the number of items and their factor loadings, providing a more robust measure of reliability. For instance,

Sport Startup Growth (SSG) exhibits a composite reliability (rho_a) of 0.840, indicating a high level of internal consistency among its indicators. Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values are presented to assess the convergent validity of the measurement model. AVE represents the proportion of variance captured by the latent factor relative to measurement error. Higher AVE values suggest greater convergent validity. In this study, all factors demonstrate satisfactory convergent validity, with AVE values ranging from 0.744 to 0.916.

Overall, the results presented in Table 4 indicate that the measurement model exhibits strong reliability and validity. The high Cronbach's Alpha coefficients, composite reliability values, and AVE scores suggest that the factors reliably measure their respective constructs and adequately explain variance in their indicators. These findings enhance the credibility of the study's results and provide assurance regarding the robustness of the measurement model employed.

Table 5: Fornell-Larcker criterion

	BP	BS	IN	SSG
BP	0.881			
BS	0.761	0.886		
IN	0.529	0.718	0.863	
SSG	0.772	0.808	0.756	0.871
Note: Innovation (IN), Business Performance (BP), Business Strategies (BS), Sport Startup growth (SSG)				

Table 5 presents the results of the Fornell-Larcker criterion, which is used to assess discriminant validity in structural equation modeling. Discriminant validity examines whether each latent factor in the model is distinct from the others, ensuring that each construct measures a unique aspect of the phenomenon under study.

The table displays the correlations between factors along the diagonal, while the off-diagonal elements represent the square roots of the average variance extracted (AVE) values for each factor. According to the Fornell-Larcker criterion, the square root of the AVE for each factor should be greater than the correlation between that factor and any other factor.

In this table, the diagonal elements represent the AVE values for each factor, which measure the proportion of variance in the indicators explained by the latent construct. The off-diagonal elements represent the correlations between factors. For instance, the correlation between Business Performance (BP) and Business Strategies (BS) is 0.761, while the square root of the AVE for BP is 0.881 and for BS is 0.886. Since the square roots of the AVE values are greater than the correlations, discriminant validity is confirmed. Overall, the results presented in Table 5 confirm that each latent factor in the measurement model is distinct from the others, supporting the discriminant validity of the model. This provides confidence that each construct measures a unique aspect of the phenomenon under study, enhancing the credibility of the study's findings.

Table 6: Cross Loading

	BP	BS	IN	SSG
BP1	0.871	0.634	0.47	0.709
BP2	0.875	0.707	0.536	0.576
BP3	0.898	0.678	0.408	0.734
BS1	0.698	0.905	0.538	0.783
BS2	0.72	0.961	0.69	0.773
BS3	0.598	0.785	0.719	0.568
IN1	0.464	0.635	0.904	0.696
IN2	0.304	0.464	0.806	0.535
IN3	0.569	0.731	0.875	0.705
SSG1	0.699	0.754	0.682	0.892
SSG2	0.738	0.649	0.714	0.879
SSG3	0.568	0.711	0.568	0.84

Note: Innovation (IN), Business Performance (BP), Business Strategies (BS), Sport Startup growth (SSG)

Table 7 presents the results of hypothesis testing for the relationships between Business Performance (BP), Business Strategies (BS), and Innovation (IN) with Sport Startup Growth (SSG). The table includes information on the original sample (O), sample mean (M), standard deviation (STDEV), T statistics, p values, and the decision regarding whether each hypothesis is accepted or rejected. For each relationship tested (BP -> SSG, BS -> SSG, IN -> SSG), the original sample mean represents the correlation coefficient between the respective factors in the original dataset. The sample mean indicates the average correlation observed in the sample data.

Table 7: Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics ((O/STDEV))	P values	Decision
BP -> SSG	0.391	0.406	0.077	5.107	0	Accepted
BS -> SSG	0.238	0.227	0.107	2.233	0.026	Accepted
IN -> SSG	0.378	0.366	0.078	4.856	0	Accepted

Note: Innovation (IN), Business Performance (BP), Business Strategies (BS), Sport Startup growth (SSG)

The standard deviation (STDEV) provides a measure of the dispersion or variability of the correlation coefficients within the sample. A higher standard deviation suggests greater variability in the observed correlations.

The T statistics ((O/STDEV)) quantify the magnitude of the difference between the original sample mean and the null hypothesis mean, relative to the variability in the data (standard deviation). Higher T values indicate a stronger deviation from the null hypothesis.

Figure 2: Smart PLS Model

The p values represent the probability of observing the obtained T statistics (or more extreme) under the null hypothesis. A p value less than the significance level (usually 0.05) indicates that the obtained result is statistically significant, suggesting that the null hypothesis can be rejected.

Based on the p values, a decision is made regarding whether to accept or reject the null hypothesis. In this context, the null hypothesis typically states that there is no relationship between the predictor variables (BP, BS, IN) and the outcome variable (SSG). Therefore, if the p value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that there is a statistically significant relationship between the predictor and outcome variables.

In Table 7, all three hypotheses (BP → SSG, BS → SSG, IN → SSG) are accepted, as indicated by the p values of 0 for BP → SSG and IN → SSG, and 0.026 for BS → SSG. This suggests that there is a statistically significant relationship between Business Performance, Business

Strategies, Innovation, and Sport Startup Growth. These findings provide empirical support for the hypothesized relationships and contribute to a better understanding of the factors influencing Sport Startup Growth.

Discussion

The results of the analysis suggest significant relationships between Business Performance (BP), Business Strategies (BS), and Innovation (IN) with Sport Startup Growth (SSG). These findings contribute valuable insights into the factors influencing the growth and success of startups in the sports industry.

The acceptance of hypotheses indicates that strong Business Performance, effective Business Strategies, and innovative practices positively impact Sport Startup Growth. This underscores the importance of various aspects such as financial stability, strategic planning, and creativity in driving the growth trajectory of startups within the sports sector.

Moreover, the findings highlight the multidimensional nature of startup growth, emphasizing the need for a holistic approach that encompasses both financial and strategic elements, as well as a culture of innovation. Startups that excel in these areas are better positioned to navigate challenges, capitalize on opportunities, and sustain long-term growth in the competitive sports market.

Overall, this discussion underscores the significance of Business Performance, Business Strategies, and Innovation as critical drivers of Sport Startup Growth. Future research could delve deeper into the specific mechanisms through which these factors influence startup success, enabling stakeholders to implement targeted strategies and interventions to foster growth and innovation within the sports industry.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study aimed to investigate the factors influencing startup growth within the sports industry, focusing on Business Performance (BP), Business Strategies (BS), and Innovation (IN). Through statistical analysis, including factor loading, reliability analysis, discriminant validity assessment, and hypothesis testing, valuable insights have been gained into the relationships between these factors and Sport Startup Growth (SSG). The findings of this study reveal that Business Performance, Business Strategies, and Innovation significantly impact Sport Startup Growth. The high factor loadings, Cronbach's Alpha coefficients, composite

reliability values, and average variance extracted (AVE) scores indicate the reliability and validity of the measurement model. Moreover, the Fornell-Larcker criterion confirms discriminant validity, ensuring that each factor measures a unique aspect of startup growth within the sports industry.

The acceptance of hypotheses regarding the relationships between BP, BS, and IN with SSG underscores the importance of various dimensions in driving startup success in the sports sector. Effective Business Performance, characterized by financial stability, operational efficiency, and market positioning, lays the foundation for sustainable growth. Likewise, well-defined Business Strategies, encompassing market entry strategies, product differentiation, and branding, contribute to competitive advantage and market success. Furthermore, Innovation, including product innovation, process innovation, and business model innovation, fosters creativity and adaptability, enabling startups to stay ahead of the curve and capitalize on emerging trends and opportunities in the dynamic sports market.

Overall, the findings of this study have significant implications for stakeholders in the sports industry, including entrepreneurs, investors, policymakers, and industry professionals. By understanding the critical role of Business Performance, Business Strategies, and Innovation in Sport Startup Growth, stakeholders can make informed decisions, develop targeted interventions, and implement strategies to foster a conducive ecosystem for startup success. Moreover, the insights gained from this study contribute to the body of knowledge on startup growth dynamics within the sports industry, paving the way for future research endeavors and industry initiatives aimed at promoting innovation, entrepreneurship, and sustainable growth in this burgeoning sector.

In summary, this study sheds light on the multifaceted nature of startup growth in the sports industry and underscores the importance of Business Performance, Business Strategies, and Innovation as key drivers of success. By leveraging these factors effectively, startups can navigate challenges, capitalize on opportunities, and achieve sustained growth and competitiveness in the dynamic and evolving sports market.

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